

Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital health Technology dEsiGn In sub saharan afriCa (STRATEGIC)

Deliverable No. D7.5

Project Website

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Abstract	This deliverable outlines how the STRATEGIC project went about developing and populating its project website.
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Revision History

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0.1	10.06.2024	B. Stahl	D. Eke	First Draft
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1 Executive Summary

This document explains the STRATEGIC project website design and implementation. It provides background and requirements and outlines fundamental decisions about infrastructure. It then describes structure and content of the website as they are available in early June 2024. 1 Background

The STRATEGIC project, as any other EU-funded project, has a duty to develop and maintain a project website. The relevant sections of the Description of Action that describe the website are the following:

“Develop resources to promote STRATEGIC and ensure a recognisable identity, creating a user-friendly website covering aims, partners, case studies, ongoing activities, results, newsworthy items and a FAQ section.” (Task 6.1)

“Early publication of preprints will be encouraged, and their dissemination will be supported by the project dissemination and communication plan. Most of these materials will also be available on the project website in an appropriate format” (Section 1.2.6; Open Science)

The website is also heavily referenced in the dissemination section of the DoA as the place where project outputs will be made available.

This deliverable outlines the design process and decisions that were made to create a website which could replicate STRATEGIC project goals, be a vehicle to convey project outputs and a resource for different stakeholders on subject related to ethics in digital health technology.

2 Technical Basis

There are numerous options that were considered as possible ways of hosting the STRATEGIC website. Hosting can happen on dedicated servers, shared servers, or by using various content management systems. The selection criteria that drove the choice of the technical infrastructure of the STRATEGIC website were:

- ease of use
- ability to easily share admin and editing rights
- accessibility
- technical robustness
- availability in areas of poor internet connection
- viability for at least 3 years beyond the end of the project
- flexibility
- value for money

In light of these requirements, it was decided to implement the website in the form of a google site, linked to an external URL.

The google site has a high level of technical sophistication and information security. It furthermore does not create any immediate financial costs, as google hosts sites for free. The site could be easily set up and was in operation at the kick-off meeting, allowing for a co-design of its initial content.

Google sites are furthermore maintained for long-term. Google as one of the pillars of the internet furthermore ensures availability of its products globally. This includes the minimization of the network traffic through appropriate technical means. Google sites are designed to work cross-platform, thus ensuring that the website will render equally well on PCs, tablets and mobile devices.

Disadvantages of this choice include a limited range of functionality and interactive design options.

The advantages of the google site choice clearly outweighed the disadvantages, certainly for the beginning of the project. In case more sophisticated functionality is required at a later stage, the website can always be migrated to a different platform.

The choice of using a google site for the project website is consistent with earlier projects where a similar setup was used, notably the ETICA project (www.etica-project.eu), CONSIDER (www.consider-project.eu) and the Responsible Industry project (www.responsible-industry.eu).

In order to ensure easy accessibility of the project website, an appropriate URL was selected and mapped to the google site, as shown in the following screenshot:

Add/Modify DNS Zone: strategic-project.orgⁱ

LCN will not be held liable for loss of service due to incorrect use of this facility. DO NOT modify your DNS settings if you are unsure how to use this facility.

Domain names ⁱ

Domain(s) *

strategic-project.org

Templates ⁱ

Apply template

Please select... ▼

A, CNAME records etc ⁱ

[+ Add records](#)

#	ⁱ Host name	ⁱ Type	ⁱ Result
1	<input type="text"/> .domain	A ▼	<input type="text" value="85.233.160.22"/>
2	<input type="text" value="www"/> .domain	CNAME ▼	<input type="text" value="ghs.googlehosted.com"/>
3	<input type="text"/> .domain	TXT ▼	<input type="text" value="google-site-verification=EU2wMMuc"/>

Figure 1: DNS configuration of the project website.

The consortium chose a URL in the .org domain, due to the international and intercontinental nature of the consortium.

3 Content

This section explains the structure of the website content as well as the design elements used to populate it.

3.1 Structure

The website at the time of preparation of this deliverable provides basic information about the project aims, its consortium, its activities and has placeholders for research outputs and other outputs, such as deliverables.

3.1.1 Homepage

The homepage includes a graphical introduction to the project as well as the project logo as seen on the following screenshot:

Figure 2: screenshot of the project homepage

More detailed information is available lower down on the page. This covers a short overview of project aims and the key project activities, as shown in Figure 3:

Project aims

The STRATEGIC project will co-create a theoretically strong, empirically supported and widely consulted responsible research and innovation approach and capacity development plan and materials that can strengthen relevant ethics and regulatory institutions for clinical trials and research in SSA.

Review

of Ethics and Legal Infrastructure for Digital Health Technologies for Clinical Research and Practice

Co-Design

of governance approaches for responsible digital health technology

Prioritisation

of sustainable frameworks

Capacity Development / Training

of National Ethics Committees, National Regulatory Authorities and other stakeholders

Figure 3: Brief project overview (bottom of project homepage)

3.1.2 Consortium

The consortium overview and links to individual members is provided on the ‘Consortium’ page which is available under this URL: <https://www.strategic-project.org/consortium>.

It starts with a group picture of the consortium

Consortium as a whole

The STRATEGIC consortium consists of seven partner organisations.

Figure 4: Consortium as a whole picture, taken during the online kick-off meeting on 01.05.2024

Each partner then has a section which starts with a link to the organisation and then lists partner representatives, their pictures and links to their institutional or personal websites, where available.

Universite de Yaounde (Cameroon)

Marceline Djuidje
Ngounoue

Wilfred Fon
Mbacham

Jude Bigoga

Figure 5: Example of a partner section

3.1.3 Activities

In addition to the consortium, there are short overviews of the main activities to be undertaken in the project. This focuses on the work in WP2, 3, 4, 5. WP1 (project management), WP6 (dissemination and communication), and WP7 (financial coordination) are not included as they are unlikely to be of interest to an external audience.

Each of these activities are listed on the homepage and have a link to a separate page that provides an overview of key activities.

Figure 6: Drop-down menu for main activities

For ease of accessibility by external audiences, short terms were used to represent the work, rather than reference to project-internal terms like ‘work package’.

3.1.4 Outputs

The website currently includes placeholders for deliverables and publications which will be populated as these become available

Figure 7: Placeholders for outputs

3.1.4 FAQs

The website includes a section on frequently asked questions which will be populated once substantial project activities commence.

3.2 Design elements

3.2.1 AI art

In order to render the website visually appealing, a set of AI-generated images have been used (see Figure 3). The following text is given on the homepage and provides the background:

“A note on the artwork on this website: As the project is concerned with digital technologies in healthcare, we wanted to explore various capabilities of such technologies. We therefore generated the pictures seen here by feeding the text of the description of the work into generative AI models and used the output to illustrate this page.”

3.2.2 Acknowledgements

The project funders are acknowledged as follows on the website:

Funded by the European Union. Complementary funding was received by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (10123282). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UKRI.

Figure 8: Funder acknowledgment at the bottom of all pages of the website.

4 Future Steps

The website fulfils all requirements in terms of accessibility and key content. It will be developed further as the project progresses. Of key importance is the dissemination and communication plan, which will rely heavily on the website and will likely require modifications.

The design of the website allows for an agile development and ensures that the website will serve the project while it runs, but also after its conclusion.